

Military Psychology In Higher Military Education The Importance Of Teaching Science

A'zamov Inom Salimjonovich

dotsent of Military Education Faculty of Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizomi

Abstract: *This article discusses the historical formation of military psychology as well The stages of development as a modern science network, its functions and structure, as well as in military educational institutions problems and prospects of introduction of psychological sciences are covered. Based on a number of psychological sources not included in scientific consumption main directions of military psychology as an independent science and future problems were analyzed. This article investigates the history and development of the military psychology as a branch of contemporary science, its structure and functions. The article deals with problems and perspectives of inclusion psychological sciences in military schools. Main directions and perspective problems of military psychology as an independent discipline have been analyzed with the help of new sources.*

Keywords — military community, psyche, moral-psychological preparation, strengthening of the human psyche, scientific psychological knowledge, military psychology, warrior personality psychology, group in the army and psychology of interpersonal relationships, military activity in peacetime psychology, psychology of military discipline, psychology of war and war.

INTRODUCTION.

Psychology in all spheres of social life today importance is growing. The field of military education is no exception not an exception. Armed with psychological knowledge military personnel plays an important role in life. It is well known that the human race is whole throughout his life he is mainly preoccupied with solving certain problems. Where there is a need, a variety of problems arise spontaneously. Big-small variety of problems haunt a person throughout his life. Simple in other words, life is a process of solving problems. Recognition a big part of the problem is that people confuse each other occurs as a result of misunderstanding. Father hand son, commander hand the soldier below, the officer in charge, or, conversely, the father of the son, the soldier mutual animosity, resentment, if the commander and the employee do not understand the leader, cakes, and even work efficiency along with suicide vs problems such as falling. Military personnel components of the psyche so that they can understand each other better they need to know. That is, in a military team or in another group they are vital and so that people understand each other positively they must be armed in a certain sense with scientific psychological knowledge. Only then the amount of problems that may arise the possibility of reduction arises.

Armed with psychological knowledge is another important aspect the aspect is that the military officer is the quality of his work and by knowing its potential to increase efficiency together predict the capabilities and behaviors of others must be able to receive. Such goals are psychological requires knowledge. It is well known that if a person lived face certain problems if he doesn't know exactly what he wants out of life is coming. Man has been able to correctly assess his spiritual potential can only succeed in life if. His own unable to

accurately assess their psychological capabilities and self-sufficient a person who does not understand the level makes a series of mistakes in life. A person who strives for perfection is psychologically always his own will need to be aware of their opportunities, successes, and shortcomings. More precisely, the ability to describe oneself as a person to step into perfection in him from the moment he has the ability opportunity arises. Implement the above goals and objectives. The mastery of psychology as a system of knowledge is a great theoretical and there will no doubt be practical help. The most important aspect of psychology that is, a person who systematically acquires psychological knowledge begins to understand himself, analyzes his successes and shortcomings, and make certain changes to them if necessary.

Psychological mastering the knowledge of a military serviceman under the command of commanders a better understanding of what is going on in his inner world, "hand to heart and the shortcomings in his mental development it is extremely necessary to correct. As well as psychological knowledge systematically mastering effective communication and communication people's mood, character, mental capacity, taste, assists in calculating interests, strengths and weaknesses can function. The study of psychology is a way to increase the mental capacity of a serviceman, strengthen memory, increase attention, creativity develop and acquire new knowledge and skills quickly and easily allows A person with certain psychological knowledge can express their opinions more accurately in speech than others and can understand the speech of others correctly; his own intellect, psychic thoroughly knows the processes and pays attention to them; mental learns ways to enhance activity as well as mental processes and systematically nurtures, heals, and shapes his psyche. We know that everyone is about the world and life in which they live has a certain knowledge. People have accumulated over a lifetime according to their knowledge "smart", "stupid", "educated", "ignorant" "capable" or "incompetent".

A soldier is committed to being the true master of his profession have knowledge and understanding of the environment is a condition. Knowledge of the universe and man, nature and society, and space using cognitive processes that are an important form of the human psyche accumulates and develops. The military is operating effectively to know their psyche, first and foremost psychological The processes must be strong in all respects. His psyche is strong and a person who is pure can easily overcome any difficult, extreme situation, can come out harmless. A warrior with a strong psyche behaves boldly in action, reliably defends the

Motherland takes Therefore, the ethical-psychological content of the individual "Strengthening the human psyche" is important in training one of the activities.

Discussion.

Equipping personnel with scientific psychological knowledge USA, UK, Russia, France, Israel and other worlds established in many developed and developing countries. The importance of the science of military psychology is great. Military psychology in Russia in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries G.E. Shumkov is one of the researchers who worked effectively with training of soldiers in times and readiness for combat situations conducted on the basis of a rigid system based on scientific psychological knowledge considered a condition.

Military psychology is the internal of servicemen and military communities studying the world and the laws of mental development of the soldier a separate branch of psychology.

The science of military psychology is as follows 5 studied in the field:

1. Psychology of the warrior's personality;
2. Psychology of group and interpersonal relations in the army;
3. Psychology of military activity in peacetime;
4. Psychology of military discipline;
5. Psychology of war and war.

The psychology of a warrior's personality. This is a military service psyche and behavior to increase the effectiveness of military work as well designed to study in order to prevent adverse events. The soldier is spiritually strong, educated and of the field. In order to professionally train commanders their psyche they will have to explore the world. Military too occur during training overcoming existing psychological problems, as well as the quality of education and development of psychological laws to increase efficiency falls within the scope of research in this area.

Psychology of military discipline. Psychological military discipline psychological analysis in order to strengthen

discipline The development of methods such as considered in the psychology of military discipline will be displayed.

Psychology of war and war. Real military action in the army to study the mental phenomena that take place in the process, to the military teaching psychological methods of maintaining mental stability, development of psychological bases of management in combat conditions etc. is a function of war and war psychology. The scope of research in military psychology is military- professional manifestation of the psyche of the serviceman in different conditions of activity features and psychological processes specific to military communities, cases and features.

Military psychology as a separate branch of psychology of the twentieth century formed in the beginning. It should be noted that statehood emerging state and after each country having its own army the question of the comprehensive development of the army commanders their army serious attention. Naturally, with the Armed Forces of the past there is a big difference between a modern army. Fight your own soldiers the commanders who led the field to inspire their soldiers before the battle used a variety of methods for the purpose. For example, the commander-in-chief the level of sensitivity of the pre-battle speech is the whole battle during which the fighting spirit of the soldiers would be in a state of uplift provided. Alexander the Great, Caesar, Attila, Genghis Khan, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur, A.V. Suvorov, Napoleon Bonaparte growing. Later socio-economic life and other great commanders inspire their soldiers who paid great attention to the issue. They are soldiers in most cases calculated by mood and needs. Great encyclopedic scientist Alexander the Great, a great disciple of Aristotle and a famous military leader always taking into account the socio-psychological factors that affect battles received He was one of the first troops to retreat during the battle that one part would frighten the other part of the army as well realized that panic in battle has a diffuse nature and tried to take action against it. Alexander the Great reputation of a commander by being able to exert psychological influence on his soldiers he also realized how important it was to gain. For example, the army precious water in a jug to the ruler at a time when he was suffering from dehydration when offered, he poured water in front of the soldiers, and so on showed that he was shoulder to shoulder with ordinary warriors.

Amir Temur was also a brave man. Entrepreneur, always select smart soldiers and help them in every way development and the discovery of new lands to take over the world, serving as the basis for the aspirations to colonize did. The cause of the First World War (1914-1918) was also the world began in order to be geographically divided. In the early twentieth century selection, training and distribution of soldiers in the army conducted mass research for the purpose. From World War II (1939-1945) then, research on military psychology in the United States intensified. Such studies are limited to military facilities not only in itself, but in agreement with various institutes of psychology were also held on the basis of.

Today, there are about 100 scientists in the United States. research centers with military-political and psychological research engaged. About 8,000 certified psychologists in the U.S. Armed Forces Hundreds of new professionals are employed every year will be taken into service. The human factor is one of the top priorities in psychological research.

Conclusion.

Within this framework, the problem of leadership in military communities is active (Stogdill, Hollander, Bass, Hebron, McGrath, Fidler, Gutskou et al.) All higher military personnel operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan psychological knowledge to prospective officers in educational institutions is systematic are taught. Psychology in higher military education, such as pedagogy, military psychology and pedagogy, aviation psychology the teaching of the sciences was introduced. In every military unit and division Having the position of a qualified psychologist is a military job will undoubtedly increase efficiency. In this regard, Uzbekistan is certain practical efforts are being made. Several higher in the republic Departments of military psychology were opened in military educational institutions. That's it along with many problems awaiting resolution. Teaching military psychology in the system of higher military education The most important issues are:

1. The direction of psychology in higher educational institutions of the republic failure to teach military psychology to the system. Training in military psychology in the system of higher military education the fact that the passing specialist himself did not pass this subject in OO will undoubtedly affect its effectiveness. Psychologists The introduction of this discipline in the military departments of universities that prepare would be a purposeful endeavor.

2. Military psychology in higher military educational institutions a large number of non-specialist staff among teachers. An educator who does not have a basic knowledge of psychology is a subject it is natural that it cannot pass effectively. In most cases, higher education four, six, or one year retraining of officers is good does not work.

3. Research work on the science of military psychology sluggish conduct. On military psychology and pedagogy and aviation psychology. The existence of numerous problems in the development of these areas, scientific requires research. In short, the psychological preparation is systematic a high level of personal content as it is conducted to combat, moral-psychological and spiritual-enlightenment training is achieved. In order to carry out professional activities effectively in them the required features are formed and developed. Military quality armament of servicemen with psychological knowledge military is one of the key factors that increase work efficiency. The refore both with the teaching of military psychology in the higher military education system The solution of related methodological issues is relevant today remains an issue..

References

- [1] 1.Sh. M. Mirziyoyev “Erkin va farovon, demokratik O`zbekiston davlatini birgalikda barpo etamiz”. Toshkent-“O`zbekiston” 2016. 14b
- [2] 2.Sh. M.Mirziyoyev “ Bilimli avlod – buyuk kelajakning, tadbirkor xalq – faravon hayotning, do`stona hamkorlik esa taraqqiyotning kafolatidir”. Toshkent-“O`zbekiston” 2019. 31bet.
- [3] 3. Sh.M.Mirziyoyevning 2022-yil Oliy Majlisga yo`llagan Murojaatnomasi.
- [4] 4. Z.Rasulova Bo`lajak o`qituvchilarning kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari SCIENCE AND EDUCATION SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL ISSN 2181-0842 VOLUME 2, ISSUE 10 OCTOBER 2021
- [5] 5. A`zamov Inom Salimjonovich. (2022). Improvement Of the Development of Tolerance Skills in Future Teachers (Example of Training a Military Course of Work). Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching, 4, 147–150. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejlat/article/view/458>
- [6] 6. Agzamov Inom Salimjonovich, & Khurramov Mansur Musurmon Ogli. (2021). ISSUES OF PHYSICAL TRAINING IN THE PROCESS OF MILITARY EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS. Archive of Conferences, 25(1), 69-72. Retrieved from <https://conferencepublication.com/index.php/aoc/article/view/1088>
- [7] 7. SALIMJONOVICH, A. I., & UGLI, K. M. M. Further Improvement of Pre-call Education in Schools. JournalNX, 6(04), 54-56. Retrieved from <https://repo.journalnx.com/index.php/nx/article/view/1817>
- [8] 8. Аъзамов, И. С., & Кочкаров, А. К. (2018). Методика применения интерактивных методов организации при проведении урочных занятий. Молодой ученый, (46), 271-274.